

MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

INNOVATIVE INSTRUMENT – "COVENANT"

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Abstract

"Tax financial engineering" means the creation of such financial products and instruments as taxes, as well as various non-tax variants of financial relations between the state and society.

"Budget financial engineering" (or financial engineering of state finances and local self-government finances) - the creation of a new financial instrument intended for the financial support of the tasks and functions of the state and local self-government bodies within the framework of the budget process. Grants, subsidies, subsidies and budget credits are examples of such instruments.

"Combined financial engineering" is a combination of two or more types of financial engineering, for example, banking and the securities market. In world practice, such structured instruments as credit default swaps (CDS) or credit default bonds (CDO) serve as an example of combined financial engineering.

This classification of types of financial engineering allows you to look at its possibilities in the field of financial risk management in a new way and can become the basis for expanding the range of application of financial instruments, changing the process of their creation and combinations of their application.

Recently, we often meet with the concept of "covenant", as an instrument of managing financial relations, which allows to distribute the financial risks of subjects. The basis of the proposed definition is a generalization of various classifications of covenants used in foreign countries, which allowed us to estimate the role of covenants in financial engineering instruments.

Keywords: financial engineering, covenant, budget

The study of the concept of the covenant from the positions of scientists and practitioners of various countries showed the absence of a single definition of the covenant, as well as general classifications that would improve the quality of the financial engineering of this instrument. However, these same materials show a high degree of demand for the covenant as a financial risk management tool in the conditions of increasing instability. Materials from Australia, Great Britain, Germany, Israel, Italy, Kazakhstan, the Netherlands, Russia and the United States were used as an information base.

The conducted analysis of many years of foreign practice showed a wide range of application of covenants as a financial instrument of financial engineering: credit relations, investments, securities market, term market, international financial agreements, pension provision, antimonopoly regulation, financing of enterprises. The consequence of this is the high demand from the participants of the credit and stock market for the services of financial engineers capable of creating the necessary financial product/instrument - covenants.

Covenants can be represented by an agreement or clause in the contract, which regulates financial relations between subjects (creditor and borrower, issuer and investor) with the aim of distributing financial risks. Therefore, the covenant is an instrument that allows you to manage financial relations and reduce the financial risk of the subjects of these relations.

The essence of the covenant is seen in the reduction of uncertainty in the future. This is manifested in

the increase in the accuracy of the forecast risk assessment by means of the preliminary determination of the responsibility of the participants of financial relations in the event of the occurrence of adverse events.

The study of materials in the field of financial engineering showed that the result of the work of financial engineers can be represented by the definitions "financial product" and/or "financial instrument".

The emergence of financial products in recent times is associated with frequent financial crises, which increase the risks of all participants in the financial market. Due to this, more complex, improved financial products are created, transforming over time into financial risk management tools.

The difference between the definitions of "financial product" and "financial instrument" is based on the following criteria: purpose of the product/instrument (purpose), form (legal layout), scope of application, period of presence on the financial market, legal status, judicial practice, margin level, number of subjects the market using this product, the volume of transactions using the financial product.

The greatest interest for this research is the financial category "innovative financial instrument", which is an intermediate option in the process of transforming a financial product into a financial instrument. The considered situation develops in a natural way, in the course of evolution, when the financial product gradually acquires a standard set of characteristics and becomes an instrument.

The difference between countries in the level of development of the financial market leads to a different

understanding of the definitions of "financial product" and "financial instrument". A financial category that is considered a financial instrument in a developed market can act as a financial product in a developing one.

At the current stage, covenants are actively used abroad as a financial instrument for managing financial risks. An analysis of Russian practice based on a comparative analysis of the definitions of "financial product" and "financial instrument" showed that covenants represent an innovative financial instrument for managing financial risks, which is gaining more and more relevance in the face of growing financial instability.

In the course of the study, it was proven that the incorporation of covenants into the structure of loans and bonds provides additional guarantees to creditors and investors, qualitatively raising the level of financial relations and improving the functioning of the financial market.

All of the above testifies to the important role of covenants in financial engineering instruments. The study of approaches to the classification of covenants existing in foreign science and practice showed the absence of a single system in their grouping and typification.

The need to generalize studies in this area is not just a desire to systematize the available material, but a practical need to identify the most effective and promising types of covenants.

In our opinion, due to the fact that covenants, as a financial instrument, must be legitimate and legal, and, therefore, reflected in the legal system of the state, we consider it expedient to propose a new classification of covenants, which has not been previously presented by other authors.

This classification is based on the legal systems of countries: Anglo-Saxon, Romano-Germanic and others.

The conducted analysis allows us to say that the number of authors-representatives of the Romano-Germanic system of law is small in comparison with the Anglo-Saxon system, and the number of covenants presented by these authors does not have a wide range. This is due to the fact that the covenants in the countries applying this legal system are more clearly reflected in the normative acts. We believe that covenants in the Romano-Germanic system form a more stable institutional environment of financial relations due to unification.

The variety of publications in the Anglo-Saxon legal system is explained by the fact that it is more casuistic and based on individual legal precedents. This system forms a less stable system of credit and financial relations, however, this makes covenants, as an instrument, very popular in the financial markets of countries that apply the Anglo-Saxon system of law.

Countries such as Israel and Kazakhstan were included in the category of other legal systems. Researchers note that the law of these countries is based on the norms of English law when applying the covenant. It should be noted that this instrument has received a legislative basis in these countries quite recently, so it is still too early to talk about the peculiarities of using the covenant in these countries.

The level of demand for the covenant is determined by the second classification feature. The analysis of foreign and Russian sources investigating covenants allowed us to identify the two most frequently used types, and, as a result, the most sought-after and time-tested covenants.

This classification allows you to more clearly structure the risks and responsibility of the parties involved in financial relations, which increases the quality of not only the financial engineering of the covenant, but the quality of the financial relations themselves.

The following classification feature was the presence or absence of financial indicators in the covenants. It should be noted that this classification feature is applied only to financial covenants that are an integral part of covenants. This allowed to deepen the research, concentrating attention only on the financial covenants that are the subject of this research.

Studies show the priority of financial covenants in comparison with other covenants, as they are designed to resolve conflicting financial issues when managing credit risk. The importance and necessity of financial covenants is explained by the fact that they show the ability of the borrower to return the necessary sums to the creditor.

In the study, financial covenants are understood as an agreement or a clause in a contract that regulates financial relations between parties (creditor and borrower; issuer and investor; etc.) with the aim of distributing financial and credit risk by characterizing the financial state through financial indicators.

Therefore, it can be said that financial covenants are an obligation to observe (positive/positive/active/affirmative) or not to observe (negative/negative/passive/restrictive) certain financial indicators at the established level during the duration of the agreement.

Based on the analysis of foreign and Russian types of financial covenants, the work proposes a universal minimum financial covenant for non-financial counterparties, which allows developing the theoretical foundations of corporate financial engineering.

During the research, it was established that financial covenants should be distinguished from financial ratios, since financial covenants can be based on financial ratios, but financial ratios themselves are not covenants.

In practice, financial covenants can be used in credit agreements, bond loans, when varying tax rates, in budgeting, derivative financial instruments, corporate agreements and many other financial relationships.

Analysis of the situation with covenants used by Russian issuers showed the predominance of type II financial covenants and a minimum of type I financial covenants.

For the transformation of financial covenants, which are an innovative financial instrument in the financial market, into the traditional instrument of financial engineering, the following institutional transformations are proposed in the study.

As part of the formation of the institutional environment for the functioning of the covenant, the following proposals were introduced at the macro level:

— to legislate the concepts of "financial engineering", "covenant", "financial covenant", which will allow to include innovations of financial engineers in financial relations;

— to introduce amendments and additions to the accompanying industry normative acts, with the aim of not only formal consolidation, but also description of the methods of practical application of the covenant;

- to establish norms in the judicial legal system for the protection of the rights and interests of the counterparties in case of violation of the covenant;

- use the Universal minimum financial covenant for non-financial counterparties as a basis for legal consolidation and practical application;

- to improve the institution of trust management (trust), to formulate the Regulation on the institution of trust, which will increase the objectivity and transparency of contractual relations containing covenants;

- it is proposed to introduce covenants into open reporting in order to expand the information base on covenants, to form statistical and scientific materials.

The above innovations allow, first, at the level of federal law to recognize covenants as a legal financial instrument, and secondly, regardless of the obligation underlying them, to give a common order of legal regulation to all covenant contracts. This will improve the quality of forecasting the results of financial relations.

Thus, the main results of the study will ensure the improvement of the efficiency of the functioning of financial engineering by using scientifically based theoretical and practical recommendations that provide the development of financial engineering financial covenants.

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